

Stability Analysis of Limit Cycle Oscillators Synchronised with the Grid Based on a Large Signal Nonlinear Method ^{*}

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Abstract

The grid synchronisation block is a key component of power electronics converters and their control systems. In some cases, synchronisation algorithms are based on non-linear oscillators and, therefore, their stability boundaries should be analyzed by using non-linear techniques. However, as this topic is relatively novel, it has been seldomly addressed in the literature. This article investigates the transient stability of limit cycle oscillators for grid-connected voltage source converters. The analysis is based on the Krasovskii theorem, which is derived from the Lyapunov theory. Numerical results are used to calculate the regions where stability is guaranteed for specific states of the synchronisation system such as the frequency, phase and voltage error. Experimental results obtained from the Power-Hardware-In-the-Loop laboratory are used to validate the theoretical developments.

1. Introduction

One of the most critical aspects in modern power systems formed by power electronic converters is their robustness against large system disturbances. Commonly, the system stability is verified by running a large number of simulations on dedicated hardware platforms. This approach reduces both the risk of performing tests in real systems and the computational time required for the tests [1, 2]. However, stability is not guaranteed from a formal perspective and there might be a real case or scenario that may push the system towards instability. The synchronisation algorithms used in the control system of grid-connected voltage source converters (VSCs) are one of the potential sources of instability. In an attempt to improve their negative impact on the system stability, some works have recently proposed the use of limit cycle phenomena derived from non-linear systems for synchronisation purposes [3]. In this sense, the limit cycle is a robust synchronisation method that is unique to nonlinear systems. One of the most relevant synchronisation algorithms based on the limit cycle is the so-called Limit Cycle Oscillator (LCO) [4, 5, 6] that has been used to generate robust references in the case of disturbances in the power grid. An advantage of the LCO is that trigonometric functions and phase-locked loops are avoided. Also, the LCO provides a robust synchronisation in many situations, and it can work in systems with both positive- and negative-sequence components, and with high levels of harmonic pollution [7].

Stability properties of traditional synchronisation algorithms (e.g. phase-locked loops) have been extensively analysed by using linear time-invariant methods such as Nyquist criterion,

Bode plot, root locus, pole placement and state-feedback [8, 9, 10]. In fact, some authors have already applied linear tools to analyse oscillators synchronised with the grid [11, 12]. However, by using these methods, only information regarding local stability near an equilibrium point is found and finding information regarding stability in a wider range of parameter variation is of great scientific interest.

In this regards, one of the most widely used tools to study the stability of equilibrium points of linear and non-linear systems is the Lyapunov's direct method. This method is commonly explained as a mathematical analogy of a mechanical system in which the energy is dissipated until the system reaches an equilibrium point. Therefore, the stability characteristics are inspected by observing changes in a scalar function that resembles the energy representation of a system (the "Lyapunov function"). Unfortunately, there are no systematic methods that are used to derive Lyapunov functions for every type of linear and non-linear system. With this respect, the Krasovskii's theorem can be in some cases applied to find a simple form of a Lyapunov function candidate for autonomous nonlinear systems [13, 14]. The main idea of the method is to check whether this particular choice indeed leads to a Lyapunov function in a certain neighbourhood. An important advantage of finding a Lyapunov function by using this theorem is that the former can be easily evaluated over a wide range of parameter variation and initial conditions. Therefore, operating regions where the function is valid can be derived. However, to the best of the author's knowledge, this theorem has not been applied so far to study synchronisation algorithms for grid-connected voltage source converters. Yet, it has been used to analyse voltage stability of single machine infinite buses and transient response of strongly nonlinear post-faulty dynamics by means of Lyapunov energy functions family [15, 16, 17, 18]. Besides, it has been used to analyse the stability of linear and nonlinear systems with time-varying delays by means of approaches to construct Lyapunov-

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Krasovskii functionals achieving good results [19, 20, 21, 22].

In this paper, a methodology to ensure transient stability of synchronisation algorithms over a wide range of initial conditions is presented. The proposed method is applied to the equilibrium point of synchronisation between an LCO - Frequency-Locked Loop (FLL) and the grid over a wide range of initial conditions of amplitude, phase and frequency variables. The stability regions in which stability is guaranteed are calculated and analysed graphically. Finally, the main theoretical developments are verified under different conditions such as voltage sags, phase-frequency variations and harmonic distortion. Both positive- and negative-sequence disturbances are tested. These experimental tests have been done so that results are comparable with other state of the art techniques [23, 24, 25, 26].

The rest of the paper is organised as follows. The dynamic model of the synchronisation algorithm is presented in Section II. In Section III, the stability analysis of a LCO-FLL is presented. Experimental results are presented in Section IV, and in Section V, a comparison with other stability analysis techniques is discussed. Finally, the conclusions are summarised in Section VI.

2. Synchronisation Dynamic System Model

A synchronisation system based on a LCO and a FLL can be written in Cartesian coordinates as follows:

$$\dot{x} = \omega \left(-\frac{x^2 + y^2}{U_p^2} x + x + y \right), \quad (1a)$$

$$\dot{y} = \omega \left(-\frac{x^2 + y^2}{U_p^2} y - x + y \right) + k_v \omega e_v, \quad (1b)$$

$$\dot{z} = -k_f x e_v, \quad (1c)$$

where x is the signal in quadrature with y and U_p is the peak amplitude for the trajectories of x and y . Gains $k_v, k_f \in \mathbb{R}^+$ modulate the signal $e_v = u - y$, which is calculated as the difference between the input signal (u) and the synchronised signal (y). Therefore, a high gain value would make the system faster. On the contrary, a small gain would lead to a long stabilisation period, thus increasing its immunity to harmonics and other possible disturbances [7].

Furthermore, the angular frequency is $\omega = z + \omega^*$, and it consists of a variable representing the frequency (z) plus a constant (ω^*). The FLL in (1c) has been introduced in [27] as an effective method for adapting the fundamental frequency of a Second Order Generalized Integrator (SOGI) [28]. Therefore, it can be seen as the product of a constant gain (k_f) and two variables: the quadrature signal (x) and the voltage error (e_v) to facilitate the understanding of the synchronisation dynamics in (1), the block diagram in Fig. 1 is provided. It can be seen that there are two outputs, namely $qu' = x$ and $u' = y$. In steady state, u' is synchronised with the input, u . One should note that U_p is a constant in (1a-1b). This makes the system (1) robust against amplitude disturbances such as spikes, notches, sags and swells, which are common in real power systems.

Normally, the references for the internal loops of VSCs are pure sinusoids (or constants in the dq reference frame).

Therefore, u has been modeled as:

$$u = U_p \sin \theta_r, \quad (2a)$$

and

$$\dot{\theta}_r = -\omega_r, \quad (2b)$$

where θ_r and ω_r are the phase reference and angular frequency reference, respectively.

In the LCO, the variable y oscillates with angular frequency ω_r and phase θ_r , while x is in quadrature with y . This situation reaches steady state when $k_v \omega e_v$ in (1b) and $k_f x e_v$ in (1c) are zero, resulting in e_v being zero as well. Thus, the system in (1) has the dynamics of a LCO synchronised with the signal defined in (2).

In order to analyse the system, the LCO-FLL model in (1) should be rewritten in polar coordinates with:

$$x = r \cos(\theta), \quad (3a)$$

$$y = r \sin(\theta), \quad (3b)$$

$$r^2 = x^2 + y^2, \quad (3c)$$

yielding:

$$\dot{r} = \omega \left(-\frac{r^3}{U_p^2} + r + k_v \sin(\theta) e_v \right), \quad (4a)$$

$$\dot{\theta} = \frac{-\omega(r - k_v \cos(\theta) e_v)}{r}, \quad (4b)$$

$$\dot{z} = -k_f r \cos(\theta) e_v. \quad (4c)$$

In this new framework, the voltage error ($e_v = u - r \sin(\theta)$) can be rewritten as the difference between u and $y = r \sin(\theta)$. Clearly, a signal in quadrature with y can be obtained as $x = r \cos(\theta)$ (this one is used in (4c), in the FLL).

3. Stability Analysis

In order to prove the local stability of the system, the set of equations in (4) should be analysed. Using the input signal (2), it can be seen that (4c) disappears as (4) synchronises with it. To account for the dynamics of (2b), a phase error variable is created:

$$\Delta\theta = \theta - \theta_r. \quad (5)$$

Therefore, the dynamics of (2) and (4) are described by:

$$\dot{r} = \left(r - \frac{r^3}{U_p^2} + k_v e_v \sin(\Delta\theta + \theta_r) \right) \omega, \quad (6a)$$

$$\Delta\dot{\theta} = \omega_r - (r - k_v e_v \cos(\Delta\theta + \theta_r)) \frac{\omega}{r}, \quad (6b)$$

$$\dot{z} = -k_f e_v r \cos(\Delta\theta + \theta_r), \quad (6c)$$

with $e_v = u - r \sin(\Delta\theta + \theta_r)$. The system (6) has the following equilibrium point:

$$x^* = \{r = U_p, \Delta\theta = 0, z = \omega_r - \omega^*\}. \quad (7)$$

Figure 1. Block diagram representing the LCO-FLL.

In order to place the equilibrium point of (6) in the origin, the following set of variables have been used to represent the system:

$$w_1 = r - U_p, \quad (8a)$$

$$w_2 = \Delta\theta, \quad (8b)$$

$$w_3 = z - \omega_r + \omega^*. \quad (8c)$$

By replacing variables in (8), the following expression is obtained:

$$\dot{w}_1 = ((w_1 + U_p) - \frac{(w_1 + U_p)^3}{U_p^2} + k_v e_v \sin(w_2 + \theta_r))\omega, \quad (9a)$$

$$\dot{w}_2 = \omega_r - \left((w_1 + U_p) - k_v e_v \cos(w_2 + \theta_r) \right) \frac{\omega}{w_1 + U_p}, \quad (9b)$$

$$\dot{w}_3 = -k_f e_v (w_1 + U_p) \cos(w_2 + \theta_r), \quad (9c)$$

with

$$e_v = U_p \sin(\theta_r) - (w_1 + U_p) \sin(w_2 + \theta_r), \quad (10a)$$

$$\omega = w_3 + \omega_r. \quad (10b)$$

Now, the equilibrium point of (9) is:

$$w^* = \{w_{1,2,3} = 0\}. \quad (11)$$

For the theoretical derivations, a vectorial function based on (9) is defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{w} = [\dot{w}_1, \dot{w}_2, \dot{w}_3]^T. \quad (12)$$

A Lyapunov function based on (12) can be defined as follows:

$$V = \mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{w}. \quad (13)$$

At this point, it is important to see the dynamic of the Lyapunov function (13) with its derivative:

$$\dot{V} = \mathbf{w}^T \dot{\mathbf{w}} + \dot{\mathbf{w}}^T \mathbf{w}. \quad (14)$$

Since $\dot{\mathbf{w}}$ is the Jacobian matrix, it yields to:

$$\dot{V} = \mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{J} \mathbf{w} + \mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{J}^T \mathbf{w}, \quad (15)$$

where $\mathbf{J} = (\partial w / \partial w_i)_{(i=1,2,3)}$. Therefore:

$$\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{J} + \mathbf{J}^T \quad (16)$$

and \dot{V} turns to:

$$\dot{V} = \mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{F} \mathbf{w}. \quad (17)$$

The terms in \mathbf{J} are:

$$\frac{\partial \dot{w}_1}{\partial w_1} = \left(1 - \frac{3(w_1 + U_p)^2}{U_p^2} - k_v \sin(w_2 + \theta_r) \right) (w_3 + \omega_r), \quad (18)$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{w}_1}{\partial w_2} = (U_p \sin(\theta_r) \cos(w_2 + \theta_r) - 2(w_1 + U_p) \sin(w_2 + \theta_r) \cos(w_2 + \theta_r)) k_v (w_3 + \omega_r), \quad (19)$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{w}_1}{\partial w_3} = (w_1 + U_p) - \frac{(w_1 + U_p)^3}{U_p^2} + k_v e_v \sin(w_2 + \theta_r), \quad (20)$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{w}_2}{\partial w_1} = -\frac{k_v (w_3 + \omega_r) U_p \sin(\theta_r) \cos(w_2 + \theta_r)}{(w_1 + U_p)^2}, \quad (21)$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{w}_2}{\partial w_2} = -k_v U_p \sin(\theta_r) \sin(w_2 + \theta_r) \frac{w_3 + \omega_r}{w_1 + U_p} + k_v (w_3 + \omega_r) (-\cos^2(w_2 + \theta_r) + \sin^2(w_2 + \theta_r)), \quad (22)$$

Figure 2. Stability region map where $\dot{V} < 0$. LCO-FLL parameters: $k_v = 1$, $k_f = 5$. Range of amplitude, phase, and frequency initial conditions evaluated around the equilibrium point: $w_1 = [-0.9U_p, 0.5U_p]$, $w_2 = [-\pi, \pi]$ rad, $w_3 = [-4, 4]$ rad/s (± 0.63 Hz), respectively. Case 1: *, Case 2: +, Case 5: x.

$$\frac{\partial \dot{w}_2}{\partial w_3} = -((w_1 + U_p) - k_v e_v \cos(w_2 + \theta_r) \left(\frac{1}{w_1 + U_p} \right)), \quad (23)$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{w}_3}{\partial w_1} = -k_f U_p \sin(\theta_r) \cos(w_2 + \theta_r) + 2k_f (w_1 + U_p) \sin(w_2 + \theta_r) \cos(w_2 + \theta_r), \quad (24)$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{w}_3}{\partial w_2} = k_f U_p \sin(\theta_r) (w_1 + U_p) \sin(w_2 + \theta_r) + k_f (w_1 + U_p)^2 (\cos^2(w_2 + \theta_r) - \sin^2(w_2 + \theta_r)), \quad (25)$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{w}_3}{\partial w_3} = 0. \quad (26)$$

It can be seen that matrix (16) should be negative definite in order to have a decreasing Lyapunov function, $\dot{V} < 0$. In this sense, by means of Krasovskii theorem [29] (see Appendix for more details), it can be proven that there are specific ranges of initial conditions where the equilibrium point (which is placed in the origin) is asymptotically stable. It is important to mention that the Krasovskii theorem guarantees asymptotic stability of an equilibrium point under specific conditions. However, there might be certain initial conditions that do not satisfy the Krasovskii theorem that the equilibrium point is just marginally stable. In other words, an equilibrium point may still be stable outside of these stability regions. Therefore, a stability region map can be generated as a function of the initial conditions. In this sense, a wide range of initial conditions for the amplitude, phase, and frequency around the equilibrium point (11) was explored for the transformed system (9). For the first test, the range of initial conditions for the amplitude were $w_1 = [-0.9U_p, 0.5U_p]$, for the phase $w_2 = [-\pi, \pi]$ rad, and for the frequency $w_3 = [-4, 4]$ rad/s (± 0.63 Hz). These values were evaluated around the equilibrium point as defined in (11). Taking these values into consideration, the stability regions were calculated. Fig. 2 (in blue) shows the region where the Lyapunov function of the system (9) satisfies $\dot{V} < 0$. In this region, it is ensured that the equilibrium point of (9) is asymptotically stable, depending on the evaluated range of amplitude, phase

Figure 3. Stability region map where $\dot{V} < 0$. LCO-FLL parameters: $k_v = 1$, $k_f = 5$. Range of amplitude, phase, and frequency initial conditions evaluated around the equilibrium point: $w_1 = [-0.9U_p, 0.5U_p]$, $w_2 = [-\pi, \pi]$ rad, $w_3 = [-256, 256]$ rad/s (± 40.74 Hz), respectively. Case 3: *, Case 4: +, Case 6: x.

and frequency initial conditions.

It is important to point out that this region becomes narrower if the initial condition variation range of the frequency in (17) is larger. This can be confirmed by observing Fig. 3, where the frequency variation range of initial conditions has been increased, making $w_3 = [-256, 256]$ rad/s (± 40.74 Hz). This variation is not realistic, but is interesting from the theoretical point of view since it produces two disconnected regions where $\dot{V} < 0$. Furthermore, if the gains k_v and k_f increase, the stability region remains unchanged, however, the performance gets faster and the immunity to the harmonics in the input signal decreases.

Moreover, one should note that matrix (16) must be negative definite in all the frequency range initial conditions for a specific amplitude and phase initial condition in order to classify it with a decreasing Lyapunov characteristic. This is done to avoid a third dimension in the region map in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3. Therefore, it is possible to find these regions theoretically and define their limits as a function of a range of initial conditions of amplitude, phase, and frequency.

4. Experimental Results

4.1. Experimental Setup

The theoretical developments were validated in the Smart Energy Integration Laboratory (SEIL) (see Fig. 4). The grid was emulated by using a 75 kVA VSC, while another VSC of 15 kVA and 8 kHz sampling frequency was used to measure the grid voltage and execute the LCO-FLL. The fundamental frequency and voltage values were set to 50 Hz and 200 V, respectively. The algorithms were implemented on embedded (real-time) computers NEXTCOM NISE3140 and the results were observed and recorded by Matlab Simulink. See [30] for a detailed explanation of the laboratory.

Figure 4. Photograph of the laboratory facilities used for testing the algorithm (Smart Energy Integration Lab).

Table 1. Cases studied and their stability properties.

Case	w_1	w_2	w_3	Guaranteed?	Stable?
1	$0.20U_p$	2.43	4	Yes	Yes
2	$-0.60U_p$	-2.24	4	No	Yes
3	$0.30U_p$	-2.49	256	Yes	Yes
4	$-0.20U_p$	1.09	256	No	Yes
5	$-0.30U_p$	1.63	4	No	No
6	$0.02U_p$	-0.87	256	No	No

4.2. Initialisation Setting Tests

The response of (9) can be, asymptotically stable, marginally stable and unstable. These type of responses were evaluated for small and large range variations of the frequency initial condition. Therefore, six experimental cases were proposed in order to verify the regions presented in Fig. 2 and 3. Thus, Cases 1, 2 and 5 correspond to Fig. 2 and Cases 3, 4 and 6 correspond to Fig. 3. Each of the experimental cases shows the transient response of the synchronised signal $y(t)$ during the synchronisation process with $u(t)$, according to specific initial conditions. Moreover, the transient response of error e_v of the LCO-FLL was measured in order to validate the stability regions calculated in Section III.

The technical details of the experimental cases are explained below. Table 1 shows the initial conditions of w_1 , w_2 and w_3 for the aforementioned experimental cases. This table also indicates if the Krasovskii theorem guarantees asymptotic stability, and if the system is stable in the real application. Fig. 5 shows the experimental waveform for Case 1, with initial conditions within the stability region of Fig. 2, where $\dot{V} < 0$. These values are $w_1 = 0.20U_p$, $w_2 = 2.43$ rad, and $w_3 = 4$ rad/s. Fig. 5 (a) shows that the signal $y(t)$ synchronises smoothly with reference signal $u(t)$ in 10 ms, approximately. Furthermore, Fig. 5 (b) shows that error signal e_v has a transient response that is asymptotically stable, as predicted in the stability region map of Fig. 2.

Another example of asymptotic stability behaviour is Case 3, which has the following initial conditions: $w_1 = 0.30U_p$, $w_2 = -2.49$ rad, and $w_3 = 256$ rad/s. In this case, the initial value of the frequency is farther away from the equilibrium point than in Case 1. However, as marked in Fig. 3, this case is still inside the stability region (i.e., $\dot{V} < 0$). As a consequence, the transient performance of $y(t)$ in Fig. 7 (a) exhibits a smooth transient response. The transient vanishes in approximately 11 ms, which is slightly greater than that of Case 1. In addition, in

(a)

(b)

Figure 5. a) Case 1. Reference signal $u(t)$ and transient behaviour of the synchronised signal $y(t)$ of LCO-FLL under specific initial conditions ($w_1 = 0.20U_p$, $w_2 = 2.43$ rad, $w_3 = 4$ rad/s) around the equilibrium point (11). b) Transient response of e_v of the LCO-FLL for Case 1 defined in Table 1.

Fig. 7 (b), the asymptotic characteristic of the transient can be seen.

In order to validate the stability limits, cases in which the LCO-FLL is marginally stable can be found. In this case, the initial conditions are outside the stability regions calculated in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3. As a consequence, the transient oscillates around the equilibrium point. For instance, Case 2, which has $w_1 = -0.60U_p$, $w_2 = -2.24$ rad, and $w_3 = 4$ rad/s as initial conditions, has this type of response. As shown in Fig. 2, this solution is located in the brown region ($\dot{V} > 0$). Fig. 6 (a) shows that signal $y(t)$ does not reach the same amplitude level of reference signal $u(t)$. However, it has the same frequency and phase. Furthermore, error signal e_v features an oscillatory transient around zero (see Fig. 6 (b)). Case 4 shows an example of this type of response, but with a farther initial condition for the frequency signal ($w_1 = -0.20U_p$, $w_2 = 1.09$ rad, and $w_3 = 256$ rad/s). As shown in Fig. 3, this case is located in the brown region. The transient response of that case can be

(a)

(b)

Figure 6. a) Case 2. Reference signal $u(t)$ and transient behaviour of the synchronised signal $y(t)$ of LCO-FLL under specific initial conditions ($w_1 = -0.60U_p$, $w_2 = -2.24$ rad, $w_3 = 4$ rad/s) around the equilibrium point (11). b) Transient response of e_v of the LCO-FLL for Case 2 defined in Table 1.

seen in Fig. 8 (a). It can be seen the output signal has a small error around the reference signal $u(t)$. In addition, Fig. 8 (b) shows that there are some oscillations in the transient of error signal e_v . As a conclusion, trajectories originated in the brown region can be marginally stable, but not asymptotically stable. However, trajectories originated in the blue region are always asymptotically stable ($\dot{V} < 0$).

Finally, there are cases in which stability cannot be guaranteed since the initial conditions are placed in the brown region of Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 ($\dot{V} > 0$). For instance, Case 5 has initial conditions of $w_1 = -0.30U_p$, $w_2 = 1.63$ rad, and $w_3 = 4$ rad/s. The results for that case can be observed in Fig. 9 (a). In that figure, it can be seen that signal $y(t)$ diverges after approximately 20 ms. Moreover, Fig. 9 (b) shows the evolution of error signal e_v during the first 18 ms before the signal diverges. Case 6 has a frequency value of $w_3 = 256$ rad/s that is even farther than the one of Case 5. Fig. 10 (a) shows transient $y(t)$ for that case, and it is clear that the system becomes unstable. Fig. 10 (b) shows

(a)

(b)

Figure 7. a) Case 3. Reference signal $u(t)$ and transient behavior of the synchronised signal $y(t)$ of LCO-FLL under specific initial conditions ($w_1 = 0.30U_p$, $w_2 = -2.49$ rad, $w_3 = 256$ rad/s) around the equilibrium point (11). b) Transient response of e_v of the LCO-FLL for Case 3 defined in Table 1.

error signal e_v in the same case. By observing Fig. 2 and Fig. 3, it can be concluded that these instability regions are mainly associated with wide variations of the amplitude and phase.

Fig. 11 shows a comparison between all the cases. It shows the transient response of error signal (e_v) during the synchronisation process for different values of the initial conditions. Cases 1 and 3 have an asymptotically stable response since they have initial conditions in the blue region ($\dot{V} < 0$). However, Cases 2 and 4 are marginally stable and correspond to the brown regions in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3, respectively ($\dot{V} > 0$). Cases 5 and 6 are also unstable, as their initial conditions are placed in the brown region ($\dot{V} > 0$) of Fig. 2 and Fig. 3, respectively.

4.3. Experimental Tests

In order to test the performance of the LCO-FLL, some additional experiments have been carried out. In particular, the response of the LCO-FLL has been verified for voltage sags and swells, frequency-phase variations, and harmonic distortion.

(a)

(b)

Figure 8. a) Case 4. Reference signal $u(t)$ and transient behaviour of the synchronised signal $y(t)$ of LCO-FLL under specific initial conditions ($w_1 = -0.20U_p$, $w_2 = 1.09$ rad, $w_3 = 256$ rad/s) around the equilibrium point (11). b) Transient response of e_v of the LCO-FLL for Case 4 defined in Table 1.

4.3.1. Voltage Swell-Sag Variation

A voltage profile with sags and swells of -0.8 p.u. and 1.1 p.u. has been used to test the transient response of the LCO-FLL. Fig. 12 (a) shows the response of the LCO-FLL for a step in the amplitude (from 1.1 p.u. to 0.8 p.u.), with a duration of 18 ms. For this sag, the frequency signal (Fig. 12 (b)) exhibits an undershoot of 0.2 Hz and a ripple of 1.8 Hz. The type of response of the LCO-FLL can be derived from the stability region map of Fig. 2. Since the sag is performed in the brown region ($w_1 = -0.2$), the frequency signal is marginally stable. However, for the variation between 0.8 p.u. to 1.1 p.u. (which happens at $t = 117$ ms), an overshoot of 0.5 Hz is produced while the ripple in the frequency becomes smoother ($< \pm 0.1$ Hz). From the stability map shown in Fig. 2, the system is asymptotically stable since the swell happens in the stability region ($w_1 = 0.1$) with a frequency variation range of ± 0.63 Hz.

(a)

(b)

Figure 9. (a) Case 5 (defined in Table 1). Reference signal $u(t)$ and transient response of the synchronised signal $y(t)$ around the equilibrium point (11). (b) Transient response of e_v for Case 5.

4.3.2. Phase-Frequency Variation.

A phase profile with a variation of ∓ 30 degrees has been applied to the LCO-FLL (Fig. 13 (a)) in order to analyse its response. First, it has been done a phase change of -30 degrees. It can be seen in Fig. 13 (b) that the frequency signal has decreased 2.5 Hz after the phase change to compensate the phase delay made in the voltage signal. After this sudden variation, the frequency is restored to 50 Hz with an exponential transient. The settling time of this response is approximately ≈ 90 ms.

After 90 ms, the phase has been reestablished, as shown in Fig. 13 (a). The LCO-FLL reacts to this sudden phase variation with an increment of 2.1 Hz above the fundamental frequency (Fig. 13 (b)). After this instant, the frequency of the LCO-FLL comes back to 50 Hz in 80 ms, approximately. As shown in the results, the transient response is asymptotically stable. This happens because the synchronisation system is operating at $[w_1, w_2, w_3] = [0, 0, 0]$, according to the regions of Fig. 2.

4.3.3. Harmonic Distortion

(a)

(b)

Figure 10. (a) Case 6 (defined in Table 1). Reference signal $u(t)$ and transient response of the synchronised signal $y(t)$ around the equilibrium point (11). (b) Transient response of e_v for Case 6.

Figure 11. Experimental results for the transient response of e_v of the LCO-FLL. Cases defined in Table 1.

(a)

(b)

Figure 12. Voltage swell-sag test. (a) Three phase voltage under a level variation of 1.1 p.u. - 0.8 p.u. - 1.1 p.u. (b) Transient response of the frequency signal under a voltage level variation.

Table 2. Harmonic distortion of input three phase voltage.

Harmonic	Seq. comp.	Mag. (p.u.)	Phase ($^\circ$)
5	-	0.1	0
7	+	0.07	20
11	-	0.05	65
13	+	0.02	5

An experimental test that takes into consideration a distorted input signal has been carried out. Harmonics 5th, 7th, 11th and 13th of both positive and negative sequence were added to the input signal. The magnitude, phase and sequence values can be found in Table 2. The three-phase waveform in the time domain can be found in Fig. 14. Also, the frequency signal is depicted in Fig. 14 (b). It can be seen that the frequency signal has a non-homogeneous ripple, which is marginally stable.

A stability region map has been computed and depicted in Fig. 15. It can be seen that the stability region has been modified compared to the one presented in Fig. 2, for the same setting conditions. Moreover, this stability region map is not symmetric, as the one in Fig. 2, due to the non-homogeneous harmonic distribution of the input signal. Furthermore, the operating point $[w_1, w_2, w_3] = [0, 0, 0]$ presents small regions where the stability cannot be guaranteed. The stability properties are worsened when the amplitude and phase variations are large.

Figure 13. Phase-Frequency variation test. (a) Three-phase voltage variation with ∓ 30 degrees. (b) Dynamic response of the frequency signal for a phase variation of ∓ 30 degrees.

Therefore, the erratic ripple in the frequency of Fig. 14 (b) is expected (approximately $\Delta f = 0.6$ Hz). The larger the amplitude of the harmonics is, the larger the ripple in the frequency becomes.

5. Comparison with other stability analysis techniques

There have not been prior publications that addressing the use of Lyapunov-Krasovskii for analysing synchronisation algorithms. However, it is possible to make a general comparison between the small-signal modelling methods for stability analysis and Lyapunov methods, even if they are applied to different systems.

One of the most used techniques for the stability analysis is based on the system small-signal modelling as described in [31, 32, 33]. This tool has been extensively used for analysing power systems and power converters, as well as for other applications in engineering fields. However, its use is restricted to regions that are close to the equilibrium point. In particular, farther away from the equilibrium point the analysis is, the worse the prediction it produces.

In the case of nonlinear stability analysis methods (in particular, the Lyapunov functions family methods), a three-dimensional graph should be analysed taking into account complex boundaries [34]. Besides, the Lyapunov functions should be adapted and evaluated under specific scenarios over several iterations of the algorithm. Therefore, this method requires a

Figure 14. Harmonic test. (a) Three phase voltage with harmonic distortion. (b) Dynamic response of the frequency signal with harmonic distortion.

Figure 15. Stability region map with an input signal that includes the harmonic distortion defined in Table 2. LCO-FLL parameters: $k_v = 1$, $k_f = 5$. Range of amplitude, phase, and frequency evaluated around the equilibrium point: $w_1 = [-0.9U_p, 0.5U_p]$, $w_2 = [-\pi, \pi]$ rad, $w_3 = [-4, 4]$ rad/s (± 0.63 Hz), respectively.

significant computational time to map all the domain. On the other hand, the proposed method is graphical and intuitive. The stability regions can be identified by means of a two-dimension graph, by just evaluating the sign of \dot{V} . However, each partial derivative of the vectorial function of the analysed system must be calculated. This means that all partial derivatives should exist and should be well defined in the domain that is being analysed [35].

6. Conclusion

In this paper, the transient stability of an LCO-FLL method for grid synchronisation has been analysed by using the Krasovskii Theorem. It has been explained how analytical analysis and numerical validation can be used to identify the regions where stability can be guaranteed. All the theoretical developments have been supported by experimental results. To demonstrate the usefulness and limitations of this method synchronisation alternative, different conditions have been tested in the laboratory. The obtained results were analysed and then compared.

The results have shown that if the initial conditions are inside the determined stability regions, the asymptotic stability is guaranteed. This was demonstrated in Cases 1 and 3. However, outside these regions, the system is either unstable or marginally stable. Cases 2, 4, 5 and 6 analysed the response of the system when the initial conditions were not placed in the stability region. Cases 2 and 4 had a marginally stable response since the synchronised signal could not reach the same amplitude level of the reference signal. However, Cases 5 and 6 were unstable in the experimental verification. In these cases, the synchronised signal diverged after a short period of time. Moreover, voltage sags and phase-frequency variations have been used to validate the types of responses in the different stability regions. Also, harmonic distortion in positive and negative sequence has been applied. In this case, the frequency signal has been analysed to verify the stability properties of the LCO-FLL.

The results are in good agreement with the theoretical analysis performed. They demonstrate the usefulness of the Krasovskii Theorem that the asymptotic stability can only be guaranteed if the initial conditions are in the stability region. Also, they show the deficiency of the method to determine the stability if the settling conditions are outside the region.

The future work will include the application of the proposed method to more complex synchronized systems such as interconnected electric generators and microgrids.

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Appendix A. Krasovskii’s Theorem

Let’s consider the following autonomous system, with the equilibrium point of interest being the origin:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) \quad (\text{A.1})$$

And $\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{x})$ express the Jacobian matrix of the system, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{x}) = \partial \mathbf{f} / \partial \mathbf{x}. \quad (\text{A.2})$$

If the matrix $\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{J} + \mathbf{J}^T$ is negative definite in a neighborhood Ω , then the equilibrium point at the origin is asymptotically stable. A Lyapunov function for this system is:

$$\mathbf{V}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{f}^T(\mathbf{x})\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}). \quad (\text{A.3})$$

If Ω is the whole state space and $\mathbf{V}(\mathbf{x}) \rightarrow \infty$ as $\|\mathbf{x}\| \rightarrow \infty$, then the equilibrium point is globally asymptotically stable [29].